

THE PROBLEM OF AGE PERIODS IN THE WORKS OF WORLD PSYCHOLOGISTS

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Abstract. *The article examines the problem of age periods in the works of world psychologists. Although our great ancestors did not study the problems of ontogenesis psychology consistently and comprehensively, in a certain direction, based on a certain concept, valuable ideas. The reflection, manifestation, development and change of these situations were described in the works of scientists.*

The above-mentioned theories, practical and scientific data, methods created by researchers retain their significance in the development of the science of ontogenesis psychology.

Keywords: *ontogenesis, psychology, consistent, complex, in a specific direction, concept, alloms, works, developments, practical, scientific, method.*

ПРОБЛЕМА ВОЗРАСТНЫХ ПЕРИОДОВ В ТРУДАХ МИРОВЫХ ПСИХОЛОГОВ

Аннотация. *В статье рассматривается проблема возрастных периодов в трудах мировых психологов. Хотя наши великие предки не изучали проблемы психологии онтогенеза последовательно и всесторонне, в определенном направлении, на основе определенной концепции, ценных идей. Отражение, проявление, развитие и изменение этих ситуаций были описаны в трудах ученых. Вышеперечисленные теории, практические и научные данные, методы, созданные исследователями, сохраняют свое значение в развитии науки психологии онтогенеза.*

Ключевые слова: *онтогенез, психология, последовательный, комплексный, в определенном направлении, концепция, алломы, труды, разработки, практический, научный, метод.*

INTRODUCTION

Although our past great ancestors did not study the problems of ontogenesis psychology consistently and comprehensively, in a certain direction, based on a certain concept, valuable opinions on the reflection, manifestation, development and change of these states were expressed in the works of scientists. They are found in four different sources. One of them is folk art: stories, proverbs, proverbs and parables; the second is advice and stories dedicated to a specific person by special creative people (even rulers); the third is encyclopedic, scientific and theoretical views of Central Asian thinkers; the fourth is the works of poets and poets who created in different periods, i.e. works of art.

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

Abu Nasr Farabi's moral and philosophical observations about man and his psyche "The City of Virtuous People", "The Essence of Matter", "Philosophical Questions and Their Answers", "Division of the Body and Accidents by Forms", "Comments", "The Meanings of Wisdom", "The Mind on Meanings" are described in a number of works. Abu Rayhan Beruni gives various information about human life in his book "Tales of the Past". Among them, the opinions expressed by the scientist about the physical structure of people, the duration and brevity of their lives deserve attention. Beruni explains the reason for human longevity by biological and genetic factors. In this regard, his works "India", "Mineralogy" and collaboration with Ibn Sina are of particular importance.

The five-volume "Laws of Medicine" by Ibn Sina contains very important information about the structure of the body, its nerves and nerve pathways, as well as psychological processes associated with physiological processes. His treatise "On Etiquette" is also a serious work on the formation of the human personality. The most important contribution of Ibn Sina to science is the scientific and practical enrichment of psychotherapy. The author is a scientist who made a significant contribution to educational psychology, psychology of ontogenesis, general, social psychology. It should be noted with pride that Ibn Sina is the founder of the science of neuropsychology. One of the main issues in the work of Yusuf Khosa Hajib "Kutadgu Bilig" is the education of a perfect person. In his work, Adib defines his principles based on how he imagined the most perfect person capable of satisfying the demands of society at that time. Other works of A. Jami "Bahoristan", "Khiradnomai Iskandari", "Tukhfatul Akhror", "Silsilatuz Zahab" express thoughts on knowledge, education, training in crafts, good qualities and decency. Davani in his work entitled "Akhlaqi Jalali" divides human qualities into four, namely wisdom, justice, courage and chastity. The poet deeply analyzes the virtue of wisdom.

In his opinion, in order to develop his mental abilities and intellectual talent, a person must be smart, intelligent, understanding and quickly acquire knowledge. In the works of A. Navoi "Khazaynul Maoniy", "Mahbulbul Gulub" and other works, there are valuable comments on morality, spirituality, attitude towards people, talents and abilities of a mature and mature person.

It is emphasized that these psychological categories are important for determining social justice. Also in the works of Navoi, a special place is occupied by the role of parents in the development of personality, the chastity of parents, issues of human modesty. Each epic of Navoi-Khamsa skillfully mixes indomitable will, volitional qualities, determination, enthusiasm, humanistic feelings, creative spirit, complex internal experiences of a person.

A. Navoi was one of the greatest representatives of Sufism. Alloma analyzed, interpreted and described 28 components of the mind.

In addition to the above, the views of Babur, Farogi, Majlisi, Mashrab, Gulhani, Nadira, Uvaysi, Mukimi, Furkat, Bedil, Zavka, Hamza, Avloni and others on the upbringing of children, morality, character, family life, interpersonal relationships are presented. relationships in works of different genres are presented briefly and concisely. Examples of psychological research in Russia began to appear in a number of oral and written, practical and scientific works concerning the human psyche under the influence of Eastern and Western culture. The first pedagogical and psychological works were written on a religious and moral basis in the 17th-18th centuries. Since the 18th century, scientific ideas have appeared on child psychology that have a certain order, direction and style. Russian historian V.N. Tatishchev (1686-1750) in his book "Conversation on the Benefits of Science and the Country of Knowledge" discusses the classification of sciences, the need to acquire knowledge, the nature of language, the meaning of the body, and the characteristics of the era. N.I. Novikov (1744-1818) puts forward the idea that it is necessary to raise children in their own way in order to disseminate useful knowledge for the benefit of humanity. His works emphasize that thinking, memory, morality, emotions and imitation are of particular importance for human improvement. It can be said that the book of A.N. Radishchev's (1748-1802) "Journey from St. Petersburg to Moscow" is actually a pedagogical and psychological work. An important role in the revival of psychology was played by the views of Russian enlighteners A. N. Herzen, N. G. Chernyshevsky, I. A. Dobrolyubov, V. G. Belinsky. A great contribution to the development of scientific psychology in Russia was made by such scientists as K. D. Ushinsky, N. F. Kapterev, I. A. Sikorsky, A. P. Nechaev, A. F. Lazursky, P. F. Lesgaft. K. D. Ushinsky "Human Education - a Subject", N. F. Kapterev "Pedagogical Psychology", I. A. Sikorsky "The Spirit of the Child", A. P. Nechaev "Modern Experimental Psychology and Its Relation to School Education", "Description of a Schoolchild" by A. F. Lazursky, "Raising a Child and Its Importance in the Family" by P.F. Lesgaft, "Description of Girls" by K. Elnitsky contributed to the acceleration of psychological development. scientific research. In Russia, the laboratory of G.I. Rossolino "Psychology and Neurology of Youth" was opened. Such journals as "Tarbiya Borisari", "Russian School", "Erkin Tarbiya", "Kundaliker" were published. That is why the "Encyclopedia of Family Education" was born. All this created a broad opportunity for the development of personality psychology and differential psychology as a science.

CONCLUSION

In the mentioned works one can see sympathy for different views and ignoring the importance of the social environment. Although the social existence of a person is recognized and interpreted from a scientific and theoretical point of view, the psychological, physiological and biological aspects and components of a person are not classified, and the external environment is explained as the main factor.

Thus, the science of ontogenesis psychology has gone through several stages of development and reached the modern level. Scientists from Central Asia, psychologists from near and far abroad have contributed to its development. The above-mentioned theories, practical and scientific data, methods created by researchers retain their significance.

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